

Deliverable N°6.3

Title: Communication and dissemination materials (Final)

Start date of the project: **November 1st, 2017** / Duration: **42 months**

Planned delivery date: M42

Actual submission date: 05/11/2021

Work package: WP6 / Task: 6.1

Work package leader: CIHEAM-IAMB

Deliverable leader: CIHEAM-Bari

Version: final

Dissemination level	
Public	x
Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. Introduction

This present document comprises the series of dissemination and communication products produced during the lifetime of the MyPack Horizon 2020 project. Consequently provides an overview of the project's constituent materials, ranging from visual identity to the project website, project leaflets, posters, introductory project PowerPoint presentation, etc. The visual identity of the MyPack project was an essential first step in establishing not only the identity for the project but also in branding the various products used to '**spread the word**' about the project. Visual identity includes the name, logo, and rules of graphic layout and the adequate use of the logo for those who deployed it, mainly by the project partners. This document also provides a brief project description and summarises the major work done on the project website and other communications and dissemination materials such as leaflets, posters and roll-up banners, screenshots of these products are also provided.

The created templates under the project's visual identity (templates for Word documents and PowerPoints) are included as screenshots in this deliverable. Moreover, a brief overview of social media communications. This deliverable aims to provide an easily accessible overview of the various dissemination and communications materials developed and available during the project's lifetime.

2. MyPack Branding

During the first four months of the project, the MyPack branding was defined to make the project easily recognisable. It represents the stable visual element for project presentation and promotion. The branding pack prepared by CIHEAM-IAMB (WP6 leader) and used by the project partners includes:

2.1. Project logo and visual identity

Great importance was attributed to the dissemination activity; a project's visual identity is of the essence to make all the disseminated documents and the applied communication products easily recognisable and identifiable.

The project logo has been designed by a professional designer and has been agreed upon by the partners.

Figure 1: MyPack logo

The visual identity is based on the key logo colours and should be respected in all official communication supports.

The colour codes are as follows:

 RGB: 241/90/47
CMYK: 0/78/93/0
ESA (web): #F15A2F

 RGB: 134/119/111
CMYK: 0/20/20/60
ESA (web): #86776F

 RGB: 200/190/184
CMYK: 22/22/24/4
ESA (web): #C8BEB8

 RGB: 97/87/81
CMYK: 54/54/55/45
ESA (web): #615751

 from
RGB: 96/122/46
CMYK: 53/12/95/44
ESA (web): #607A2E

to
RGB: 214/222/112
CMYK: 23/0/68/0
ESA (web): #D6DE70

 from
RGB: 137/3/3
CMYK: 9/98/100/41
ESA (web): #890303

to
RGB: 235/28/35
CMYK: 0/98/98/0
ESA (web): #EB1C23

 from
RGB: 35/31/31
CMYK: 80/84/66/92
ESA (web): #231F1F

to
RGB: 109/110/112
CMYK: 54/44/41/31
ESA (web): #6D6E70

 RGB: 35/31/31
CMYK: 80/84/66/92
ESA (web): #231F1F

2.2. Slogan

The project slogan is: « **Sustainable Packaging Solutions** ».

3. Communication and dissemination materials

Based on the project logo and visual identity, other branding elements were developed and are represented here in screenshot exemplars.

3.1. Communications: Templates for Word and PowerPoint

➤ Graphical templates:

A set of graphical templates (PowerPoint, Word) was designed to ensure professional design and presentation in all the project documents and communications.

All the graphical templates are available in the private website section "intranet".

Figure 6: MyPack letterhead template

<p style="font-size: small;">Project funded by H2020 Programme Grant Agreement number: 774265 The information contained in this communication only reflects the author's view</p>	Dissemination level		Public		Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC		Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)										
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Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)																	

Figure 7: MyPack deliverable template

MYPACK PROJECT
ANNUAL CONSORTIUM MEETING

Place
date

WP. «.....»

TITLE
Name – Institution (country)

 MP MyPack

 Sustainable Packaging Solutions

 Project funded by H2020 Programme
Grant Agreement number: 774265
The information contained in this communication only reflects the author's view.

Title

 Project funded by H2020 Programme
Grant Agreement number: 774265
The information contained in this communication only reflects the author's view.

2

 Project funded by H2020 Programme
Grant Agreement number: 774265
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3

 MP MyPack

THANKS!

Sustainable Packaging Solutions

 Project funded by H2020 Programme
Grant Agreement number: 774265
The information contained in this communication only reflects the author's view.

Figure 8: MyPack presentation template

MyPack External Communication Reporting Form

Name of the event	
Dates of the event	
Venue	
Type of audience: <input type="checkbox"/> The scientific community (higher education, research) <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> End users <input type="checkbox"/> Policymakers <input type="checkbox"/> Wider public	
Type of activity <input type="checkbox"/> Publication <input type="checkbox"/> The organization of the Conference <input type="checkbox"/> Organisation of Workshops <input type="checkbox"/> Webinars/Applications <input type="checkbox"/> Press releases <input type="checkbox"/> Films <input type="checkbox"/> Articles published in the popular press <input type="checkbox"/> Videos <input type="checkbox"/> Media briefings	
<input type="checkbox"/> Presentations <input type="checkbox"/> Oral presentation to a wider public <input type="checkbox"/> Oral presentation to a scientific event <input type="checkbox"/> Exhibitions <input type="checkbox"/> Posters	
Size of audience	
Countries addressed / represented	
Partner involved (name of the person)	
Title of presentation/paper (if applies)	

 Project funded by H2020 Programme
 Grant Agreement number: 774265
The information contained in this communication only reflects the author's view

Figure 9: MyPack external communication reporting form

➤ **A generic project presentation:**

Following the MyPack branding, a **generic MyPack presentation** (<https://cloud.mypackfood.eu/index.php/s/oETXueloJcEsg2z>) was developed to be used for awareness-raising and information at events and via the partners' networks. It was used by all persons involved in the project to disseminate the project objectives, its status, and the expected results. It was adapted by partners for specific audiences and updated with new information. It details first the project's structure in terms of objectives, the main results that the project aims to achieve and the tools that the project uses. The presentation aims at attracting the interest of relevant communities and stakeholders.

3.2. Dissemination products

A series of printed products were required for the project's; specifically, this includes many leaflets/brochures, posters, and roll-ups used in different events.

➤ **Flyers/leaflet:**

A MyPack flyer/leaflet was compiled and used to present the project and its goals. It also provided an overview of the consortium and contacts: significant contacts, website.

This leaflet was widely used at several events and continue to be useful for the remainder of the project.

The project	Objectives	Case studies
<p>The goal of MyPack is to support the market introduction of innovative packaging in order to reduce both food and packaging waste and their negative influence on the environment.</p> <p>An important parameter for evaluating packaging is its optimal environmental impact. For such a concept to success, the consumers also need to participate. Information, awareness raising, and dissemination of the advantages are key elements in this.</p> <p>That is why MyPack aims to include the various expectations from different consumer groups related to product sustainability, handling, and product safety and quality in the project.</p> <p>New packaging can be adapted to many different consumer expectations. MyPack strives to find the best possible products and the best possible market for the commercial development of <u>innovative packaging technologies</u>.</p>	<p>MyPack will provide general guidelines to select the best market for a new technology. These guidelines will provide tools and methodologies to packaging and manufacturing industries, for an appropriate commercial development strategy taking into account:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ The environmental efficiency; ☞ The consumer adoption; ☞ An optimized industrial feasibility <p>These general objectives will be developed for two groups of packaging technologies:</p> <p>1-Promote the development of bioplastic packaging:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ Promote the commercial development of biodegradable and compostable packaging; ☞ Promote the commercial development of packaging from renewable resources; <p>2-Promote the development of elaborated (high barrier and active) packaging technologies.</p>	<p>MyPack project will focus on the following technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ Biodegradable packaging: bio-based and biodegradable materials and multilayer film technology; ☞ Barrier complex film improvement: high oxygen barrier packaging by microlayer multiplication technology, and replacing EVOH by PA; ☞ Rigid and soft bio-packaging: heat resistant PLA (regid packaging) and soften PLA (film applications); ☞ Innovative breathing film: microtechnology insertion conferring film breathing properties; ☞ Packaging barrier coating: SiOx inert barrier; ☞ Antimicrobial packaging; ☞ Renewable barrier packaging:PEF renewable substitute of PET.

<h3>Consortium</h3> <p>MyPack is composed of a large consortium involving partners from the academic, scientific and industrial world, including SMEs.</p> <p>www.mypackfood.eu</p>		
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Figure 2: MyPack flyer

➤ Roll-up and posters:

A set of roll-up stands and posters was developed and shared with partners to visually support project communication at events. It is an effective way to display the project's visual identity while ensuring that the audience knows who the organiser is/which project is behind the event.

Figure 3: MyPack general poster also used as roll-up

Two posters have been set up for presenting the project online at the 5th European Bioplastics (EUBP) Conference, in December 2020 and at the 6th International ISEKI-Food Conference in June 2021.

Both posters are available in the section [MyPack in events](#).

Figure 4: MyPack poster presented at the 5th EUBP Conference

Figure 5: MyPack poster presented at ISEKI-Food 2021

4. MyPack Online communication and dissemination

4.1. Website

The first version of the MyPack website has been available since Month 6 (<http://www.mypackfood.eu/>). It provides a responsive design to display correctly on any device (from regular PC to mobile devices).

The MyPack website represents the first vehicle in raising awareness of the project and contains a general presentation of the project objectives and the consortium and all public information related to the project activities, results, events, etc. It follows the MyPack branding and plays an essential role in the information campaign.

Project funded by H2020 Programme
Grant Agreement number: 774265

The information contained in this communication only reflects the author's view

The website's content was updated periodically (especially concerning the information on project publications and events) and on-demand (e.g., when important news must be published).

The project website points to all the targeted audiences of the project (stakeholders, researchers, potential end-users, policymakers, general public). In addition, it presents a general introduction to the project and its potential impact, even for an audience unfamiliar with the subject.

The homepage is clear and offers users the possibility to learn more about the MyPack project. Next to this, the homepage allows users to be informed about the different technologies used in the project framework and follow the latest news and relevant events.

The website also serves as a launch site for the forthcoming project newsletters, project youtube channel and social media platforms (Twitter and LinkedIn).

Figure 9: MyPack homepage

4.2. Social Media – Strategy outline

The project team placed great emphasis on creating a MyPack community consisting of people who are/ may be interested in MyPack implementations. In this context, the project team exploited the power of social networks and available internet tools to enable more effective dissemination to the community. The ultimate goal was to create a MyPack "virtual" community that is flexible enough to engage its members during the project's periods and activities.

Specifically, MyPack established profiles on professional social networks such as LinkedIn, Researchgate and Twitter. These are used as direct communication channels with other professionals from relevant fields. In addition, the networks are regularly updated with the events, news, or state of the project to increase the impact of the MyPack project.

4.2.1. LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a Professional Network through which MyPack can address particular professional target groups. It is mainly functional for targeted networking and to create a sustainable MyPack network in which the status of the project but also project outcomes can be shared.

The MyPack project disposes of a shared LinkedIn account with the YPack, Horizon 2020 project since both are focused on sustainable packaging. With the need to avoid splitting an audience that can be far larger with one consolidated professional group. In this respect, the group was named "[Bioplastic and sustainable food packaging](#)", the number of members is increasing encouragingly; we reached **1,103 members**.

Figure 10: MyPack group on LinkedIn

4.2.2. ResearchGate

ResearchGate is a large academic, social networking site for scientists and researchers. It is mainly functional to disseminate the project outcomes and share the publication with the scientific audience.

The [MyPack Group](#) in ResearchGate was set up in month 10. The group built more connections to people within the research group and beyond, and till now, it reached **39 followers and 289 reads**.

Figure 11: MyPack group in ResearchGate

4.2.3. Twitter

Twitter is extremely useful to inform and engage with our target audience groups and their respective communities. Building a community/being part of an already existing community is crucial for dissemination via Social Media platforms. Information about the latest updates on the website, new events, discussions and news were provided via Twitter.

MyPack project used the available hashtags such as #sustainablepackaging, #packagingsolution, #foodpackaging, #foodwaste, #packagingwaste, #HorisonEU, to connect to existing communities. Once a significant number of followers was established, we built our hashtag: #MYPACKnews. From December 2019, the [MyPack Twitter](#) account reached **123 followers** with more than **200 tweets**.

Figure 12: MyPack Twitter account

4.2.4. YouTube

YouTube is highly regarded as an advantageous dissemination channel for video content. Therefore, MyPack set up a google-account and activated its YouTube channel "[MyPack Food](#)".

From creating the MyPack Food channel (February 2019), videos were published to disseminate the project output and webinar recording. The channel counts **18 subscribers** and more than **1,370 views**.

Figure 13: MyPack Food YouTube channel

4.3. Newsletter

The purpose of the newsletter is to disseminate information on the project to interested audiences. It primarily addresses subscribers interested in the subject matter of the project.

Access to the newsletter was possible through a) the project website and b) delivery through email following subscription. The subscription ensured that every new newsletter issue was sent directly to the subscribers' mailbox.

During the MyPack project lifetime, three newsletters were produced and distributed among the partners and subscribers. Moreover, a section was dedicated to subscribing to the MyPack newsletter and downloading the latest issue on the website homepage.

The MyPack newsletters provided information about the project objectives and achievements as well as on upcoming events.

The first MyPack newsletter was descriptive of the project objectives and the proposed packaging technologies. Then, a newsletter session was dedicated to describing similar Horizon 2020 projects GLOPACK and YPACK (<https://mypack.voxmail.it/p/kisn5r/c-58f2b753>).

Additionally, the second MyPack newsletter was dedicated to the study led by 2B in the framework of Work Package 3, which concentrates on "Food waste data and environmental assessment" with the purpose to identify and optimise food-packaging market clusters, selecting the best packaging solutions for different applications through two methodologies: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) <https://mypack.voxmail.it/p/wre7sz/c-12aceb13>

However, the last newsletter was mainly dedicated to the innovative packaging solution "Breathable packaging with BlowDevice microtechnology" developed in the framework of the MyPack project and patented by Basilicata University (UNIBAS) and NINETEK (both are project partners). The focus on this technology was decided after the European Commission (EC) recognised Blow[®] micro-technology as a "Key Technology" in Europe on [the Innovation Radar Portal](#).

All published newsletters are available on the MyPack website, section [newsletters](#).

4.4. Press releases

Mainly after the recognition of Blow[®] micro-technology as "Key Technology" in Europe by EC, several newspapers, specialised magazines and TV channels highlighted the results achieved and promoted the developed technology at the European level. All the published newspapers and videos are available on the project website, section [Press releases](#).

4.5. Free joint webinars

To overcome the delay in communication and dissemination activities due to the COVID pandemic, the MyPack project organised a series of free webinars with other like-minded European projects: [YPACK](#), [GLOPACK](#) and [CIRCUL-A-BILITY](#)., to disseminate together, maximise the impact of results on the market, and minimise overlaps.

MyPack organised a series of successful webinars with EU-funded projects GLOPACK and YPACK on different topics:

- Challenges and opportunities of bioplastics for packaging
- The impact of packaging on the environment and how to balance with food waste
- Consumers' acceptance and perception of sustainable packaging

Over 319 professionals from 32 countries and different stakeholder categories, mainly from the scientific community, packaging and food industry, in addition to civil society and international organisations, registered to the three events held online on October 28th, November 27th and December 15th 2020. The participants expressed high interest by engaging in an interesting discussion at the end of each webinar. The webinar presentations and video recording are available on the project website, session [MyPack in events](#).

Moreover, the MyPack project renewed its experience with a cost action project CIRCUL-A-BILITY. Over 109 participants from 30 countries (EU and non-EU)and different fields, mainly research community, packaging

and food industry, civil society, and international organisations, registered to the events. During the event, the partners discussed the following issues in an engaged debate with the participants:

- Packaging and Sustainability;
- Sustainability communication to consumers;
- Circular packaging design;
- Sustainable disposal behaviour of packaging;
- Consumers' perception of sustainable packaging;
- The gap between current developments/activities and communication on packages;
- Research needs;
- Current research activities within MyPack and COST Circul-a-biltiy, European projects.

The webinar presentations and video recording are available on the project website, session [MyPack in events](#).

4.6. MyPack education

In November 2020, the MyPack project multiplied the short communication through social media with key messages addressed to a large audience, including stakeholders. MyPack short communication complemented that published by the project YPACK and GLOPACK, since MyPack project includes also elaborated packaging as Blow[®] microtechnology at the difference of the two other projects, which include only biodegradable and compostable packaging.

Through the Twitter account, the MyPack project announced the idea of developing education cards or videos in the form of questions/answers addressed to a wide audience to promote the project outputs through **#MyPacknews**, with 224 views.

The first cards were addressed to the **dissemination of Blow[®] microtechnology device**. The first one was articulated as a question: "Did you hear about breathable packaging" (with 556 views); and the second card contained a definition of breathable packaging with an introduction of MyPack Blow microtechnology with their advantages (1,571 views).

CIHEAM BARI

MP MyPack

Did you hear about BREATHABLE PACKAGING?

Breathable packaging allows constant and passive gas exchange between the food and the external atmosphere, avoiding the complete depletion of the oxygen.

In the framework of MyPack project, UMIBAS and MINETEK developed an innovative device, based on micro-technology named **Blow®**; that device can be inserted on the packaging layer, to control gaseous exchange between the inside and the outside of the package.

Advantages of Blow® micro-technology device

- Easy application with different kind of packaging;
- Able to modulate and allow gas exchanging in both direction;
- Helps to avoid fog inside the package and asphyxia issues during storage;
- Extends shelf-life of highly perishable fresh food products.

On 20 July 2020 the European Commission recognised Blow® micro-technology as "Key Technology" in Europe on the Innovation Radar Portal
https://www.innovradar.eu/innovat_en/21832

Figure 14: 1st education cards

The 3rd card was dedicated to **food waste** and its negative environmental impact. The card illustrated that by throwing away food with an example of 1Kg of tomatoes (we chose tomatoes because it is widely consumed in Europe and the world), you are wasting the product and the resources (e.g. water, land & energy) that went into making it. For example, one kilo of tomato waste is equivalent to one car's CO₂ emission on the road for two km. With the slogan "All together to reduce food waste and preserve our planet". The project tweeted this card twice, and the overall views were 4290.

 Figure 15: 3rd education cards

The last posted short communication on September 2021 was in video format related to the third card dedicated to packaging waste.

The [video](#) illustrated the active contribution of packaging waste to climate change, intending to raise public awareness and show the trade-off between packaging and food waste with a new concept. 2B partners calculated the CO₂ impact to produce three types of packaging to pack a half kilo of tomatoes (paper bag, mixed packaging with paperboard tray and PE film; and PET tray) and that for the production of the packed tomatoes. The video exposed that using a single kind of packaging corresponds to the waste of a percentage of tomatoes. For example, using a paper bag to pack ½ Kg of fresh tomatoes corresponds to the waste of two packed tomatoes, representing 5% of the entire tomatoes inside the bag. However, using mixed packaging with a paperboard tray and PE film corresponds to the waste of five packed tomatoes, representing 14% of the entire tomatoes inside the bag. Nevertheless, the application of PET tray packaging corresponds to the

waste of eight packed tomatoes, representing 22% of the entire tomatoes inside the bag. This video collected more than 700 views.

4.7. Announcements poster

The announcement of several workshops and webinars has been published online, including a web form for registration. In addition, the announcement posters have been distributed for major promotion among the MyPack partners, project social media, and CIHEAM Bari networks in Mediterranean countries (e.g. FTN).

MyPack project developed five announcement posters, and all are available on the project website in the section [news](#).

Sustainability communication on food packages status quo and future needs

Free webinar organised by MyPack in collaboration with COST action CIRCUL-A-BILITY, European projects

July 5th, 2021
10:00 to 11:30 am CEST

[Free registration](#)

Agenda

10:00-10:20
Giulia Granato
WUR, Netherlands
"A meaningful reminder on sustainability: when explicit & implicit packaging cues meet"

10:20-10:40
Prof. Victoria Krauter
FH Campus Wien, Austria
"Circular packaging design and communication"

10:40-11:30
General discussion

Moderator
Prof. Giancarlo Colelli
UNIFG, Italy

Figure 16: Webinar announcement poster

MyPack

Sustainability communication on food packages – status quo and future needs

Free webinar organised by MyPack in collaboration with COST action CIRCUL-A-BILITY, European project

5th July 2022 (10:00 - 11:30)

sdmama@karni.it
https://www.mypackfood.eu/

Email:

Surname:

Name:

Stakeholders category

- Researcher (Scientific Community)
- Policy maker
- Food industry
- Packaging industry
- Civil society organisations
- Consultant
- Waste management
- Other (specify):

Organization:

Homepage

- Word of mouth
- Social media (e.g. Twitter, FB)
- Website
- E-mail
- Other (specify):

Captcha code: **triking**

Security code:

I have read and accepted the privacy policy

I'm aware and I agree to the webinar recording

